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Attitudes of Teachers towards the Development of Achievement Motivation in Primary Schools in Nnewi North Local Government Area of Anambra State

By

Dr. P.C Okafor

Institution: Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University
Department: Educational Foundations
Telephone: 09039449219

Corresponding E-mail: Patokafor2001@yahoo.com

Abstract

Primary school teachers, like all other teachers in different sectors of education, have a set of roles to perform, to enable the predetermined objectives of the primary school to be attained. According to Idumanje (2002), motivation is generally regarded as the drive to achieve targets or goals, and therefore must be maintained for academic achievement. Motivation provides an important foundation to complete cognitive behavior, such as planning, organization, decision-making, learning, and assessments (Pintrich & Schunk, 2006).

Achievement motivation for Reynolds (2006) can be conditioned in individuals at the early state of life through training, experiences and subsequent learning. Furthermore children usually acquire the achievement motive from their parent's lifestyle and teachers' attitudes. Studies on attitude of teachers towards developing achievement motivation in pupils have shown that, children whose independent training starts at an early age and those whose teachers give more autonomy within a cooperative, encouraging and less authoritarian classroom environment usually develop an achievement oriented attitude. These key areas were investigated by the researcher to establish development of achievement motivation among primary school pupils. This study therefore propose to explore attitudes of teachers towards the development of achievement motivation in primary school pupils very relevant among school pupils

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INTRODUCTION

According to Drever (2000), teaching is an art and the quality of teaching depends on the love, dedication, and experience of the teacher towards the subject or the content. The attitude of a teacher is a teacher characteristics and component of the teacher personality. These attitudes, particularly as teachers impact knowledge on the learned, can have important implications for teacher-pupil interaction, pupils' academic aspirations, academic motivation and academic achievement of pupils. Therefore achievement motivation is influenced by these factors that affect students perceptions of the academic setting that is the classroom environment. According to McClelland, Atkinson, Clark and Lowell (2003), several internal and external factors contribute to a student's achievement motivational orientation in the classroom, these include recognizing the relationship between effort and ability, understanding the classroom reward structures, balancing academic mastery and social competence, and choosing tasks of appropriate difficulty. Teachers have hands in helping academic achievement (Drever, 2000).

Atkinson and Feather (2006) suggest that achievement motivation is a combination of two personality variables: tendency to approach success and tendency to avoid failure. Bigge and Hunt (2000) defined achievement motivation as the drive to work with diligence and vitality, to constantly steer towards goal realization, to obtain dominance in challenging and difficult tasks and create sense of achievement. This definition consists of three elements: the stimulation of personal capabilities, constant effort with drive and obtaining of sense of satisfaction. Achievement motivation therefore is a subjective and internal psychological drive, enabling individuals to pursue work they perceive to be valuable and promoting them to reach their goals. Different types of academic motivation have different implications for academic achievement. If a student has high levels of academic motivation, knowing whether that student is extrinsically or intrinsically motivated may be important in making predictions about that students' academic career (Hofestein and Lunetta, 2002). Therefore primary school teachers necessarily require a reasonable level of attitude to enhance achievement in pupils for academic achievement.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

For many years, examinations have been accepted as an important aspect of the educational system. Examinations have always been used as the main basis for judging student's ability and also as a means of selection for educational advancement and employment. Every year, thousands of pupils sit for the common entrance examination. This examination is done at the end of the sixth year of primary education. Over the years, discrepancies have been observed in the performance of pupils in the examination. Although pupils may be of comparable abilities, learning in the same environment and following the same syllabus, their academic performances still vary.

Also, there are pupils who may be bright but perform poorly despite the good learning facilities in their schools. Among the factors that are blamed for pupils' poor academic performance are teachers attitude. Teachers at times pay little or no attention to the development of achievement motivation of one word pupils. They tend to give closer attention to the high achievers than how achieving pupils. Thus, low achievers may feel dejected and may withdraw from participating in classroom activities. This therefore may not hamper only their self image but may lead to pupils' poor academic performance/achievement. How then can pupils be helped out of this situation. Perhaps, consideration of teacher's attitude towards pupils' development of achievement motivation may answer the question. Therefore the study filled the

gap of lack of current information pertaining teachers attitude towards the development of achievement motivation in primary school pupils very relevant among school pupils

Objective of the Study

The objective of the study was to investigate teachers attitude towards the development of achievement motivation in primary school pupils very relevant among school pupils. the study sought to investigate;

1. The role of teachers towards the development of achievement motivation in primary school male and female pupils;
2. Strategies to enhance development of achievement motivation among primary school pupils.

Research Questions

1. What role does teachers play towards the development of achievement motivation in primary school male and female pupils;
2. What are the Strategies to enhance development of achievement motivation among primary school pupils.

Literature Review

Previous studies carried out by school and authors in the areas teachers attitude towards the development of achievement motivation in primary school pupils will be review under the following sub-headings

Conceptual framework

Theoretical framework

Empirical studies

Summary of Review of Literature

Conceptual Framework

Concept of Attitude: An attitude is an expression of favour or disfavor towards a person, place, thing, or event (the attitude object). Prominent psychologist, Gordon Allport once described attitude as the most distinctive and dispensable concept in contemporary social psychology. Attitude can be formed from a person's past and present (Allport, 2005). In a lay language, attitude may refer to the distinct concept of mood, or be especially synonymous with teenage rebellion. An attitude can be defined as a positive or negative evaluation of people, objects, events, activities, ideas, or just about anything in your environment, but there is debate about precise definitions. Eagly and Chaiken (2006) for example defined attitude as "a psychological tendency that is expressed by evaluation of particular entity with some degree of favour or disfavour (Eagly and Shally, 2008). Though it is sometimes common to define an attitude as affect toward an object, affect (i.e. Discrete from attitude as a measure of favorability (Ajzen, 2001).

The definition of attitude allows for one's evaluation of an attitude to vary from extremely negative to extremely positive, but also admits that people can also be conflicted or ambivalent toward an object meaning that they might at different times express both positive and negative attitude towards the same object. This has led to some discussion of whether individual can hold multiple attitudes toward the same object (Wood, 2006).

Concept of Teacher: A teacher is one that teaches; especially one whose occupation is to instruct. According to Wikipedia (2013), a teacher or school teacher is a person who provides education for pupils (children), students and adults. The role of teacher is often formal and ongoing, and is carried out at a school or other places of formal education. In many countries, a person who wishes to become a teacher must first obtain specified professional qualifications or credentials from a university or college. These professional qualifications may include the study of pedagogy, the science of teaching (Fraser and fisher, 2002). Teachers, like other professionals, may have to continue their education after they qualify, a process known as continuing professional development. Teachers use a *lesson* plan to facilitate student learning, providing a course of study which is called the curriculum.

Hartmut (2008) uphold that a teacher is a person whose occupation is teaching others, especially children, teacher's role may vary among cultures. Teachers may provide instruction in literacy and numeracy, craftsmanship or vocational training, the arts, religion, civics, community roles, or life skills. A teacher who facilitates education for an individual may also be described as a personal tutor, or, largely historically, a governess. In education, teachers facilitate student learning in a school or academy or perhaps in another environment such as outdoors.

Wittenberg (2009) opined that a teacher who teaches on an individual basis may be described as tutor. The objective is typically accomplished through either an informal or formal approach to learning, including a course of study and lesson plan that teaches skills, knowledge and/or thinking skills. Different ways to teach are often referred to as pedagogy. When deciding what teaching method to use, teachers consider students' background knowledge, environment, and their learning goals as well as standardized curricula as determined by the relevant authority. Many times, teachers assist in learning outside the classroom by accompanying students on field trips. The increasing use of technology, especially the rise of the internet over the past decade, has begun to shape the way teachers approach their roles in the classroom. Teaching using pedagogy also involves assessing the educational levels of the students on particular skills. Understanding the pedagogy of the students in a classroom involves using differentiated instruction as well as supervision to meet the needs of all students in the classroom. Pedagogy can be thought of in two manners (Moos, 2009). First, teaching itself can be taught in many different ways, hence, using pedagogy of teaching styles. Second, the pedagogy of the learners comes into play when a teacher assesses the pedagogic diversity of his/her students and differentiates for the individual students accordingly.

Concept of Achievement Motivation: Achievement contexts can be found anywhere-on the playing field, on stage, in an art studio, or even in a kitchen or a garden. To be sure, standards and even the definitions of success vary among contexts. In sports success usually means winning, although it could also be defined in terms of personal improvement. Success for a pianist might be measured in the length of applause or in newspaper reviews, for a hostess in the amount of food the guests consume, and for a surgeon in patient survival rates. Atkinson, Clark and Lowell (2008) defined the need for achievement (achievement) as "success in competition with some standard of excellence". That is, the goal of some individual in the story is to be successful in terms of competition with some standard of excellence. The individual may fail to achieve this goal, but the concern over competition

with a standard of excellence still enables one to identify the goal sought as an achievement goal. McClelland et al (2008) went on to describe that competition with a standard of excellence was most notable when an individual was in direct competition with someone else but that it can be evident in the concern for how well one individual performs a task, regardless of how someone else is doing. According to Lussier and Achua (2007), the need for achievement is the unconscious concern for excellence in accomplishments through individual efforts. Similarly, Daft (2008) stated that the need for achievement is the desire to accomplish something difficult, attain a high standard of success, master complex tasks, and surpass others. Individuals who exhibit the need for achievement seek to accomplish realistic but challenging goals.

Theoretical Frame work

Achievement Motivation Theory: The theoretical framework for this study was rooted in McClelland's achievement motivation theory. "Achievement motivation theory attempts to explain and predict behaviour and performance based on a person's need for achievement power, and affiliation" (Lussier and Achua, 2007). The achievement motivation theory is also referred to as the acquired needs theory or the learned needs theory. Daft (2008) defined the acquired needs theory as McClelland's theory that proposes that certain types of needs (achievement, affiliation, power) are acquired during an individual's lifetime'. The Achievement motivation theory evolved from work McClelland began in the 2000s. In 2008 McClelland described human motives in the methods of measuring human motivation chapter of Atkinson's book, motives in fantasy, action, and society. At that point, McClelland identified human motives related to the achievement motive, the affiliation motive, the sexual motive, and the power motive. In his later work, the achieving society (McClelland, 2001), however, McClelland focused his attention on only need for achievement, the need for affiliation, and the need for power. In essence, McClelland theory postulates that people are motivated in varying degrees by their need for achievement, need for power, and need for affiliation and that these needs are acquired or learned during an individual's lifetime (Daft, 2008, Lussier and Achua, 2007). In other words, most people possess and will exhibit a combination of three needs.

Cognitive Theory: Cognitive theory is not satisfied with merely observing behavior and its consequence. It may want to assess students' beliefs about the consequences of behavior or the causes of performance outcomes. It may also want to measure how competent the students believe themselves to be in a particular domain, whether they expect to succeed or whether they believe grading is fair. The intervention cognitive theory would design a program aimed at changing (maladaptive beliefs and are based entirely on previous experiences with contingencies (e.g. reward and punishment) to one's own behavior. People's expectations are based on many factors, such as observations of what happens to others when they behave in a particular way, or even simply what they are told about what they can expect. When teachers call attention to the consequences of students' behavior, they are attempting to influence behavior by influencing expectations about the consequences of desired behaviors.

Empirical Studies

Bassey, S. and Akpan, R. J. (2010) investigated the relationship between achievement motivation among primary school teachers and institutional effectiveness in terms of teaching and learning, community-school partnership, professional leadership, staff and students in Nigeria primary schools. The population of study was made up of all primary school teachers, while sample consisted of 240 respondents randomly selected from administrative and teaching staff. A 35-item questionnaire in two parts constructed by the researchers was used to gather data while Pearson's product moment correlation analysis was employed for data analysis. Findings revealed significant relationships between achievement motivation and institutional effectiveness in teaching and learning ($r = 0.72$), community-school

partnership ($r=0.66$), professional leadership ($r = 0.64$), staff and students' involvement ($r = 0.56$), and high intellectual expectations ($r = 0.49$). On the basis of the findings and conclusion, it was recommended that job enrichment should be applied in the job description of primary school teachers, achievement motivation workshops should be arranged for department heads. The reviewed study and present study differs in population and sample size. The reviewed study focused on relationship between achievement motivation among primary school teachers and institutional effectiveness in terms of teaching and learning, community-school partnership, professional leadership, staff and students in Nigeria primary schools while the present study focused on attitudes of teachers towards the development of achievement motivation in primary school.

Aydin and Coskun (2011) investigated the relations between the achievement motive of secondary school students and the relations between end of the study, the arithmetic mean of the views of students, the achievement motive, "gender," "class level," "Parent education level" and "family income level" were the variables. Total of 15 students studying in high schools in the city center of Karabuk in the academic year of 2010-2011 participated in the research survey model used in the study. "The Achievement motive scale" was used as data collecting tool developed by Ellez (2004). The descriptive statistics, t-test and one way variance analysis (ANOVA) were used in the analysis of data. At the end, the scale of the achievement motivation has been determined to be 3.74. The views of students about the scale of geography lesson achievement motivation has shown significant difference according to "class level," but did not show any significant difference according to "gender", "mother's education level", " father's education level" and "family income status". Based on the findings of the study, suggestions for increasing the achievement motivations of the students towards geography curriculum have been developed. The reviewed study focused on academic achievement of Secondary school students, while the present study focused attitudes of teachers towards the development of achievement motivation in primary school.

Velmurugan and Balakrishnan (2013) investigated the achievement motivation of primary school pupils in relation to locality and type of family. The study was conducted on a random sample of 600 students studying in Ariyalu and Perambalur districts in Tamil Nadu. The achievement motivation test constructed and validated by Gopal Roa (1974) was used to collect the data. The result of the study revealed that there is no significant difference between the rural and urban school pupils in their achievement motivation. Also, it is inferred that there is no significant different between the general stream primary school pupils coming from joint family and nuclear family in their achievement motivation. The reviewed studies differs from the present studies both in population , sample size and location. Both studies were carried out in Nigeria.

Summary of Review of Related Literature

The attitude of teachers towards the development of achievement motivation in primary school pupils has been reviewed. Since need for achievement vary from one student to another, the attitude of the teacher may help in planning activities, know where students stand, and which students. From the reviewed literature, scholars suggested that achievement motivation is a combination of two personality variables - Tendency to approach success and tendency to avoid failure. The review suggests that achievement motivation is a subjective and internal psychological drive, enabling individuals to pursue work they perceive to be valuable and prompting them to reach their goals. Scholars suggested that individuals who are high in need for achievement are concerned with making better their own performance and that of others. Achievement motivation can be effectively developed in the primary school pupils where staff and pupil sizes could be classified as small and medium-sized. Furthermore, achievement motivation theory and cognitive theory were found to be relevant to the study. On the

whole, empirical evidence suggests that children often have goals that are different from the teachers, thus achievement motivation is a table learned characteristic in which satisfaction comes from striving for and achieving a level of excellence.

Methodology

The design adopted for this research was descriptive survey method which aims at assessing the perception of students on lecturers computer literacy skills used in teaching and learning in Colleges of Education in South-east Nigeria. According to Nworgu (2015) a descriptive survey research are those studies which aim at collecting data and describing in a systematic manner the characteristics features or facts about a given population. The study was conducted using questionnaire designed to be descriptive. The sample consisted of two hundred (200) respondents selected through purposive sampling techniques. A total of 20 schools were selected from the 45 primary schools in Nnewi North Local Government Area. The instrument used for data collection is a questionnaire titled 'Teachers Achievement Motivation Rating Scale' (TAMRS). Which contained nineteen (19) instruments items on a four point scale of strongly agree (SA= 4 points), Agree (A= 3 points), Disagree (D= 2 points) and strongly disagree (SD = 1 point). In analyzing the data, the researchers used weighted mean score and standard deviation in answering the research questions.

Results

1. What role does teachers play towards the development of achievement motivation in primary school pupils

Table 1: Respondent mean on What role does teachers play towards the development of achievement motivation in primary school pupils

S/N0	ITEM STATEMENT	SA	A	D	SD	FX	X	REMARKS
1	encouraging discipline in the classroom	80	60	30	20	580	3.05	Agreed
2	to control noise making in the classroom	30	40	50	70	410	2.16	Disagreed
3	improving teachers interaction in the classroom with learners	70	55	50	15	560	2.95	Agreed
4	promoting better teacher-pupil-relationship	70	70	35	15	575	3.03	Agreed
5	teachers improve on their classroom control during delivery of instruction	80	80	15	15	605	3.18	Agreed
6	Use of standardized teaching aids	80	70	10	30	580	3.05	Agreed
7	Exposing the pupil with outside knowledge	50	100	20	20	560	2.95	Agreed
8	Teachers development an motivation can eradicate lateness to school	45	70	45	30	510	2.68	Agreed

9	Demonstration method improves pupils motivation and achievement developmt	50	70	60	10	540	2.84	Agreed
10	Classroom motivation assist teachers apply appropriate instructional methodology in class	75	75	20	20	585	3.08	Agreed
	Grand mean(x)						2.89	Agreed

2. What are the Strategies to enhance development of achievement motivation among primary school pupils.

Table 2: Respondent mean score on Strategies to enhance development of achievement motivation among primary school pupils.

s/n	ITEM STATEMENT	SA	A	D	SD	FX	X	REMARKS
1	to communicates new ideas to the pupils	100	40	30	20	600	3.16	Agreed
2	creating room for exchange of ideas among pupils	70	60	40	20	560	2.95	Agreed
3	Provision of opportunities for analysis of new ideas	115	45	20	10	645	3.39	Agreed
4	Offering of incentives from the teacher	65	80	25	20	570	3.0	Agreed
5	creating forum for making useful suggestion for solving educational problems	60	50	50	30	520	2.74	Agreed
6	improving pupils knowledge and skills	45	60	60	25	505	2.66	Agreed
7	Proper conduct formative assessment by the teacher	40	60	70	50	500	2.63	Agreed
8	Workshop equip teachers with necessary strategies for instructional development	100	20	80	20	580	3.05	Agreed
9	opportunities to attend competition improves pupils motivation	55	80	45	20	570	3.0	Agreed
	Grand mean(x)						2.95	Agreed

Result of the findings

After the data analyzed, the following is the summary of the findings:

Classroom motivation influences teachers' pupils achievement in Nnewi north and also Workshop technique influences teacher job performance in primary school.

Further more, result of the analysis of data presented in this study confirmed that teachers motivation help pupils form good habits at earlier stage and also teachers should be enriched by building into individual, greater scope for personal achievement, recognition and responsibility. The result of this study showed that children that attended primary school perform better in secondary school. It is also seen that achievement motivated people seem to be more concerned with their personal achievement rather than the rewards of success.

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